

Unlocking the Future of Data-Driven Collaboration- Shaping the Horizon of Open Science and Industry Innovation

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1. Preface

This report provides some reflections on the presentations and discussions that took place during the final workshop of the EU project MatCHMaker¹ on 29th of May at the Société Géologique de France in Paris. The workshop was co-organised with the European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC)² and hosted by the Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA)³. This report is an appraisal of the event and not an accurate summary of presentations or discussion contributions.

2. Introduction

Project MatCHMaker comprised twelve partners from eight European countries who came together to better understand the link between advanced materials properties and complex microstructural features. They worked on a model-based innovation process to accelerate the design of advanced materials for three specific cases in the construction, energy and mobility sectors. Their methodology was based on three pillars, i.e., advanced data acquisition, machine learning (ML) tools, and physics-based models. It was of importance to enhance the interoperability and integration of characterisation and modelling data and workflows through a semantic approach, and create an open data repository based on semantic representation to connect design and manufacturing processes. The project has interesting findings so another aim of this last workshop was to encourage industry to adopt and further some of them.

On a national level, a representative of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research and Space, could confirm that the project aligns well with the aim of strengthening the sovereignty and competitiveness of the European industry. In particular, advanced materials are recognised as a key driver for innovation, resilience, and industrial leadership in Europe. MatCHMaker was specifically acknowledged for:

- Advancing microstructural characterisation of materials.
- Usage of physics-based modelling capable of predicting meaningful materials properties
- Creation of standardised databases enabling ML
- Provision of three industrial use cases driven by the shared objective of reducing carbon dioxide emissions

The MatCHMaker beneficiaries dedicated time towards data sustainability and consistency, developed within a computational ontology framework, which will contribute to broader European initiatives on open and interoperable data repositories. Hence, the foundations have been laid for continued coordinated progress between a variety of future stakeholders.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101091687>

² <https://emmc.eu/>

³ <https://www.cea.fr/english/Pages/home.aspx>

3. Results & Industrial Exploitation Pathways

The project beneficiary Heidelberg Materials⁴, one of the major cement manufacturers in the world, found itself confronted with a carbon permit price of € 74 per ton of CO₂, which is actually higher than the cost of production of cement. One of the fastest ways to decrease their CO₂ emission consists of blending cement with Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCM) such as limestone, clay or similar. The challenge they face now is, if one blends the cement with a novel SCM, will its performance stay the same? There are also health and safety issues, as clay for example, contains quartz and the dust could damage workers' lungs. To analyse the strength and durability of cement, one has to look at its microstructure, and MatCHMaker developed an image analysis tool for microscopy images of these new cements. Besides this image analysis tool, they have also developed (physics and data-based) models to predict the strength of these new cements.

Outcome: Heidelberg Materials will expand to new SCMs and will use the above workflows and methods in the near future.

GENVIA⁵ produces Solid Oxide Fuel/Electrolysis Cells (SOFC/SOEC) and in MatCHMaker the focus was on cell technology, aiming to improve performance and mechanical robustness of their electrochemical cells. The degradation mechanism is linked to nickel particulate agglomeration, and cracks in the materials can decrease the durability of these cells. Without understanding of the cracking threshold, the design of cells remains empirical. Also here, MatCHMaker developed image analysis tools which helped the company to analyse their cell material much faster. The experimental results are used to calibrate a phase-field model, developed in the frame of MatCHMaker, that simulates Ni-reoxidation and crack appearance. This model will ultimately be used to identify the best microstructure for a highly performing electrode with good mechanical robustness.

Outcome: GENIVA can understand and simulate the physics of their materials in more depth and with the tools developed, speed up their characterisation process.

During the work on the use cases, many data were produced and beneficiaries from SIMAVI⁶ were working against data being scattered in different places with different formats. They have designed and implemented the Matchmaker Open Repository (MOR), which is a common environment where researchers, industry partners, and technical partners have access and can collaborate. Their first step was to give data a meaning: data were catalogued and described. Then, it was important to understand the context; this means how the different data sets are related to people, projects, characterisation procedures, etc. Domain ontologies have been developed in this project, i.e. the Domain Ontology for Concrete (DOC)⁷, the Domain Ontology for Microscopy (DOM)⁸, and the Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Domain Ontology⁹. Thus, data is given meaning through annotations and ontologies. The repository comprises also a set of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools that allows users to ask questions in natural language.

Outcome: new domain ontologies; data could be accessed easier and connected to existing data sets. The MOR could be reused and embedded in existing ecosystems, as it is domain agnostic.

⁴ <https://www.heidelbergmaterials.com/en>

⁵ <https://genvia.com/>

⁶ <https://simavi.ro/en/home-2/>

⁷ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-concrete>

⁸ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-microscopy>

⁹ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/domain-sofc>

Within the MOR, there are tools that have been developed for the three use cases. For Heidelberg Materials, Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) is harnessed to obtain the chemical composition of cements. An ML workflow was developed that can analyse images and quantify each phase inside it; thereafter a physics-based model is used to explain the evolution of the cement paste. At the moment, this tool needs to be supervised by a human expert user and is thus, semi-automatic. However, the obtained data were sophisticated enough to train an unsupervised ML model. Hence, there is also a second, fully automated tool, that can use only the Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) images, which are faster to acquire; there is a limit, as only the main phases of the cements can be analysed. The tool was trained on the optimal acquisition conditions, so an expert has to monitor deviations to make sure results are reliable.

GENIVA deploys for its fuel cells similar image analysis workflow as described for cements, which is rather time consuming. MatCHMaker beneficiaries have developed a deep learning tool that also uses the faster acquired EBSD images. The image processing time decreased from a few hours to minutes. If there are ambiguities in an image, they are flagged from uncertainty estimation methods, and a human expert can revisit specific parts on an image and re-analyse them. Again, the model has been trained on specific acquisition conditions, and has to be retrained, if these are changing. A future development could be to add more relevant data and generalise the algorithm to make it more robust.

For Proton-Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFC), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) is the modality of imaging, and the objective is to identify nanoparticles inside these images. The sizes of these nanoparticles are related to the performance of the electrodes. The analysis tool "draws" boxes around the image of each nanoparticle and creates a histogram distribution of the sizes. One limitation of this tool is that very small nanoparticles are hard to detect. It is also of interest to accelerate the image acquisition process by using neuronal networks which can improve the signal-to-noise ratio. Hence, the image acquisition time could be reduced by a factor of 4 or 10, depending on the quality required. For the moment, there is a possible loss of contrast, but post-processing algorithms may be able to overcome this limitation.

Outcome: MatCHMaker successfully developed tools that can reduce the time, cost and risks of developing and optimising advanced materials.

Project MatCHMaker, as common in such EU projects, has dedicated tasks to exploit their project outcomes, i.e., the MOR. A joint ownership will be formalised, so each developer gets full credit for their work. The objective of the first year past project, will be the full operational alignment of the repository with the FAIR principles. A further development may be to integrate the MOR to European data spaces and marketplaces to then maximize the cross-domain interoperability. Community onboarding should happen early and be enabled with a freemium access. During this time, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) will be increased, and at some point, services around the MOR could be monetised. The latter could comprise bespoke model development and repository-as-a-service provisions.

The primary markets are the sectors materials informatics (20% CAGR¹⁰), the construction sector (6.7 – 8.5% CAGR), and fuel cells (20% CAGR). Secondary markets may be found in R&D departments of materials manufacturers, academia, developers of ML/AI models, and also standardisation bodies.

Outcome: The Matchmaker Open Repository is positioned as a first-of-its-kind distributed data and knowledge mesh, acting as a digital bridge between the academic research and the industrial application.

4. Panel I: From Project Results to Industrial Adoption

Ideally, EU projects should help the EU based industry to become more competitive, by transitioning their outputs to industrial adoption. Several of the panel participants had experience in being beneficiaries of EU projects and, thus, gave valuable insights. The best scenario to immediately adopt a project outcome in industry, is that it finds its way into a beneficiary's R&D department as a daily tool or method. This is rarely the case; but if the outcome is of great interest, a company might consider funding an internal project to carry on and deploy at pilot scale. Great interest can be triggered if the new product or process outperforms in a use case with respect to what is in place at an industrial partner's site. Also, there needs to be the capacity (people, lab space, equipment) to run such a pilot. This is particularly difficult when the project outcome is software and none of the beneficiaries is a software owner. Software needs developers, maintenance, upgrades and continuous updates. It also needs domain specialists who understand the users and can provide them with the right tools. But having users means they will need training and support, so that they can use the software adequately.

Developments like the MOR, have potential to become domain agnostic, from a developer's perspective. However, the users then tend to bring a plethora of domains, often unknown to the software developers. There are some research and technology organisations (RTOs), which can be mediators between software and a few expert domains. RTO means that they have room to experiment with these tools, and that they have projects with industry where they can advise on how to work with a particular software and the corresponding data.

To push a tool like the MOR further, the whole community involved in sectors construction, energy and mobility would need to support such endeavour. Development work and maintenance can be shared, communities support each other, and also can report in early which direction needs to be taken to make MOR attractive for the work to come. The emphasis should also not lie on the products a sector has, but on the common workflows they tackle. To enable the community to join, the licensing has to be setup most likely as open-source. Still, the developed software has to be verified and validated. Such tools enable service providers to create jobs for themselves around such a technology stack, such as building bespoke solutions for a particular industry. Software always needs data, and the community will have to agree on how data (information) should be organised and standardised.

The EU, which is a community, is encouraged to move away from judging projects solely by reports, and thus, honour the achievement of individuals. It could be of interest, to rate a project by how

¹⁰ Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) is the average yearly rate at which a value grows, assuming the growth is steady and compounded each year.

many steps they have taken towards the wider community who could profit from their outcomes. The latter takes time and this should be considered in the description of action and when budgeting for projects. The EU is using subject matter experts and monitors for projects and the projects themselves have steering committees and advisory boards – these people could be a good source to point towards communities, exploitation opportunities, etc., which could make a project's outcome even more visible.

Software needs to be kept somewhere and needs infrastructure to be deployed. Many organisations such as EMMC or The Innovative Advanced Materials Initiative (IAM-I)¹¹, do have many experts in the field amongst their members, but both of these organisations do not have funding for hosting software nor can they apply to the EU for funding it. The EU does have The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)¹² as a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest and the latter lies in the biological and medical sciences. The materials community would have to come up with an idea for an e-infrastructure which has a high impact on Europe and concentrate on what the very diverse materials sciences have a common need of.

5. Data Lifecycles & Non-Technical Barriers

In a previous workshop¹³, beneficiaries of MatCHMaker and its sister projects discussed the data life cycle, its pain points and good practices. They realised, that the technical infrastructure for FAIR data already exists, and that it has matured, but that it is not really adopted. Interestingly, the constraints are not just technological, but the human, organisational, and policy environment in which the technology is asked to operate. Eight interviews with persons involved in EU projects and 13 inputs from an online survey led to the following list of what keeps people from good data management (DM) practices:

- Time: DM is a non-urgent task so it moves to the bottom of a to-do list
- Data management plans (DMPs) are a compliance artifact – duly filed for a funding body, but never really looked at
- The non-existence of “double-hatted” persons, i.e., domain experts with DM skills
- Sub-culture: people who produce a lot of data need to manage them to understand them; they tend to establish an individual culture of handling data
- Research data need to be researched; they do not exist a priori to a project – which makes them hard to be described or managed
- Low motivation due to cost: the data producer invests, but they may not be the data consumer of the future – why invest if one will not use?
- Non-existence of agile project management; research data are evolving at different times and do not align with project review meetings; also, the ontologies needed, often arrive at a later stage of a project

¹¹ <https://www.iam-i.eu/>

¹² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en

¹³ Ouzia, A., Daniel, G., Friis, J., Ghedini, E., Imrich, P., de Marchi, J., Nahshon, Y., Rohrhofer, F. M., Schmid, S., & Simperler, A. (2025). Workshop on Data Lifecycles in the World of Materials Modelling and Characterisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992583>

The publish or perish culture does not help, either – a PhD student is often rated by their published paper output, but never if their DM was done perfectly or at all. Researchers in industry are asked to develop new materials, or manage many projects at the same time; also, here the DM can fall short.

DM can be a job for a full-time employee and some universities and industry settings are looking for so called data stewards. At the moment, there are no good job descriptions and career paths available and organisations like the Careers and Skills for Data-driven Research (CaSDaR)¹⁴ Network try to change this. When one realises the need of DM, they just find their own way of getting it done which leads to a plethora of DMs for each lab, research group, etc. Also, once a DMP is established and working, those individuals tend not to change their habits for a 3–4-year EU project. Similar to the use of software – one will switch if the “new software” is at least 20% better and then makes the effort and onboarding worthwhile. Onboarding to a new DM style requires change management and the the Prosci ADKAR¹⁵ model can help here. ADKAR stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement.

Awareness: is DM is essential?

Desire: do we want to do it?

Knowledge: what tools will we use to do it?

Ability: can we do it?

Reinforcement: is somebody checking on us doing it?

Awareness is the easy part as many EU project participants are involved in data sharing, semantics, interoperability; so eventually it sinks in that data need to be both managed and FAIR. Also, knowledge can be easily satisfied as there are tools and good practises around. The desire to do it is rather low – good DM takes time one does not have and may require stopping the old way of DM. A remedy could be to give time to do DM and time to learn something new and undergo a culture change in DM as part of a project objective. To give a project a better ability to delve into better DM practises, a (automatised) provision of meta data right at the source could help. All this change in behaviour could be reinforced by faster reporting cadences, i.e., the reporting aligns better with the data’s journey along the data life cycle. To enable this, data stewards should be budgeted for when applying for EU or multilateral projects. They will be responsible for a test review of the actual implementation midterm of the DMP, and assure that there is a metadata model anchoring at proposal stage. There could well be an external service, for example data stewarding-as-a-service provided by the EU. In an ideal DM scenario, three months before the 1st reporting period of an EU project, the data steward would interview all the persons who produce data and help them building a data model. That shall be repeated for the mid-term and final reviews and, thus, the reinforcement is naturally provided by the data steward themselves.

¹⁴ <https://casdar.ac.uk/>

¹⁵ Hiatt, J. M. (2006). ADKAR: A Model for Change in Business, Government and Our Community. Loveland, CO: Prosci Learning Center Publications.

The EU certainly should play a part, but responsibility for good DM lies within every organisation, who may need to adapt in how they recognise the data work, and by hiring data specialists.

6. Materials Commons as a Strategic Exploitation Platform

Timely, with MatCHMaker coming to an end, Materials Commons¹⁶ is starting on 1st of June 2026. It is a strategically composed and highly complementary consortium funded under the call HORIZON-CL4-INDUSTRY-2025-01-MATERIALS-45: Materials Commons for Europe (IA)¹⁷ whose shared mission is to drive forward innovation and cross-sector collaboration in materials science by establishing a federated digital infrastructure that seamlessly connects researchers from both industry and academia. Their approach is fully aligned with relevant innovation strategies, policies, and programmes across Europe, ensuring coherence, scalability, and long-term impact.

Materials Commons attempts to be a federated system that connects everything a digital materials researcher needs, i.e., experimental and computing infrastructures, workflows, data, repositories, etc. Interested persons can be service prosumers; they can provide something for and consume something from this system. In short, the joint mission for the European materials community will be to create this pioneered federated digital infrastructure adapted for the materials research domain.

There will be semantic interoperability in the background and in the foreground user-friendly templates that allow researchers to deposit their data regarding input, output, process steps, characterisation/modelling results, etc. Besides accessing this manually, templates could be machine action enabled or even been driven by Large Language Models (LLMs). Characterisation and modelling often encompass complex workflows and there will be ways to digitise those. All of these digital assets (data and workflows) need to be connected and interoperable to become building blocks for complex protocols. There is no coherent practice to annotate data; one is confronted with different silos of metadata and different approaches individual industry sectors have developed. However, there are some vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies around that could form the basis of a more coherent way of storing information. Specialised service provisions around Materials Commons will enable data consumers to make the most of it. Not all data consumers may be humans; hence, it will be necessary to have a representation of information that somehow makes sense for a robot in a lab, AI in the cloud and, still, a human operator in between.

With LLMs at each persons' fingertips, the question may arise, why bother with Materials Commons, if a prompt can access all digitised data anyway. For example, a single dataset could be easily converted by an LLM to a publication ready figure in short time. However, doing the same operations for 1000s of data sets would be extremely costly as LLMs scale poorly. Still, LLMs will have their place and are a really important aspect in orchestrating research workflows and optimising experiments especially if they are connected to a persistent knowledge layer such as a knowledge graph that is built on proper semantics.

Materials Commons is envisaged as a platform for the many excellent laboratories across Europe who could expose their local data repositories, workflows, and services to a wider audience. What will not happen is that organisations will share their actual data freely due to IP issues. What they

¹⁶ <https://www.materialscommons.eu/>

¹⁷ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-CL4-INDUSTRY-2025-01-MATERIALS-45

can do is sign a non-disclosure agreement with a potential partner they want to work with and share data privately via the Materials Commons framework that can provide the architecture to make data interoperable.

7. Panel II: Open Data, Standards, Policy & Strategic Outlook

Larger characterisation facilities with external users such as synchrotrons naturally have data standards and policies in place as they have to consider what works well for all users. Smaller laboratories rather consider what works best for them as external users rarely have to be considered. What helped was the advent of Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) where users are obliged to enter metadata in order to do calibrations or data analyses – but only there where they are used.

One of the first persons that needs to be converted to data management would be the Principal Investigators (PIs); this may well be happening via the petition of students as the younger generation is a little bit more open to ideas for better data management and open science.

Interestingly, large characterisation facilities also started to care about what their users could do better with their data analysis. To start with, they produced and provided data, and then the users were responsible for their own analysis workflows. However, the users may not tap into the full potential of the data obtained; so, providing them with analysis tools and protocols make them value the facility much higher and generate returning custom. The users, who have expert data analysis skills tend to write their own (Python) scripts and move further off-standard. They are also less open to reconsider their established workflow and accept a more standardised one.

A good strategy to implement more standardised data practised could be creating positions for data stewards that can help researchers to do so. Institutions employing data stewards notice more ELN implementation, usage of DM tools and workflows, which means that data are very well described, i.e., have metadata. In an ideal world, a repository could be built with the metadata model, and the person who is defining the data structure from application profile for semantic profile would be a data engineer or data manager. This also shows, good DM requires a team of experts rather than a jack-of-all-trades. Even if one gets the right humans in the loop, instrument vendors still tend to offer specific data formats with different ways to create meta data. Not having a common format of the raw data makes DM really challenging.

As discussed already in Chapter 5, many (EU) projects do generate a DMP, but then lack the implementation. Hence, one needs a dedicated data manager who works with beneficiaries to achieve this implementation. However, there also needs to be some incentive and vision from the funding bodies, as “generosity for the next generation” may not always be a strong driver.

What will need to be discussed further, is what data should be stored and could be reused. There is little appetite on investing a lot of work to make data FAIR which are hardly reused. Sometimes, it was more beneficial to retain a sample and redo a measurement when and if needed. Often, data is not reused because it's not reusable, so it is a kind of a chicken-and-egg problem.

A good example are protein structures for the bio community; the Worldwide Protein Data Bank had 4.7 bn downloads in 2025.¹⁸ The materials sciences have so many different characterisation tools that

¹⁸ <https://www ww p d b . o r g / s t a t s / d o w n l o a d>

the costs of standardising data produced with them may be too costly to be beneficial. However, what takes hold of materials sciences are robots in autonomous labs, and these rarely complain about documenting data properly. Hence, automation may naturally lead to FAIR data in materials research. One also needs to consider that scientific papers are a researcher's interpretation of the data, so what a human may take with a pinch of salt, AI could take at face value. Hence, governance is very important, so Materials Commons could become an overarching entity that scores tools, workflows, databases, etc. as trustworthy/FAIR/standardised to encourage reuse rather than people redoing all again and again.

What differs humans from AI is the capability of questioning themselves: why did one look at a particular sample, why did one take a certain decision, why did they move on to something else? If thought processes could be logged, maybe new ideas¹⁹ could be thought of rather than a repetition of an old idea.

8. Conclusions and Outlook

MatCHMaker has successfully provided and demonstrated the benefits of analysis workflows for the characterisations of new advanced materials in the sectors construction, energy and mobility, respectively. Their efforts were appreciated by both a representant of the French government and external participants. Both physics and data-based modelling were used to interpret advanced characterisation outputs. It was clearly demonstrated, how this can aid the expert with repetitive or tedious task, and the emphasis was on enhancing the experts' work rather than replacing it. Experts via a panel discussion gave constructive advice on how to best lift digital developments such as the MOR from the drawing board to real life. It was noted that the results of the project can be translated into workflows for other industries. The support of the community is needed to further the development of such digital workflows and aid with translating them from domain specific (use-case) to domain agnostic. The MatCHMaker project devoted some time to research the non-technical barriers preventing researchers of DM and a second panel discussion gave more insight to this topic. Materials Sciences are diverse and involuntarily tend to create silos around expertise; however, there is common ground such as data formats and schema which are domain agnostic. This and other starting points will find an application in Materials Commons, a federated digital infrastructure that seamlessly connects researchers from both industry and academia over a wide range of materials science domains.

¹⁹ " *There is no such thing as a new idea. It is impossible. We simply take a lot of old ideas and put them into a sort of mental kaleidoscope. We give them a turn and they make new and curious combinations.*" Posthumously (1912) Vol.3. in Mark Twain: A Biography: The Personal and Literary Life of Samuel Langhorne Clemens by Albert Bigelow Paine.

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10. Disclaimer

All statements of fact, opinion, or analysis expressed in the report are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information used and statements of fact made are not guarantees, warranties or representations as to their completeness or accuracy. The authors assume no liability for any short term or long terms decision made by any reader based on analysis included in this report. In many cases, the opinion expressed in the reports is our current opinion based on prevailing trends and is subject to change.

11. Acronyms, Abbreviations and Elucidations

ADKAR - Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement

AI – Artificial Intelligence

Beneficiary - Beneficiaries are the legal entities involved in an EU project covered by a grant agreement.

CAGR - Compound annual growth rate

CEA - Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives

DM - Data Management

DMP - Data Management Plan

DOC - Domain Ontology for Concrete

DOM - Domain Ontology for Microscopy

EBSD - Electron Backscatter Diffraction

EDX - Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy

ELN – Electronic Lab Notebook

EMMC – European Materials Modelling Council

EU – European Union

FAIR – Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable

IP – Intellectual Property

LLM – Large Language Model

ML – Machine Learning

MOR - Matchmaker Open Repository

PEMFC - Proton-Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells

PI - Principal Investigator

R&D – Research and Development

SCM - Supplementary Cementitious Materials

SOEC – Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells

SOFC - Solid Oxide Fuel Cells

TEM - Transmission Electron Microscopy

TRL – Technology Readiness Level

12. Appendix A: Workshop Schedule

Jointly organised by the European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) and the MatCHMaker EU project, hosted by CEA and took place in Paris, 29th May 2026.

Time/CET	Speaker	Topic
9:00 – 9:30	Registration & Networking	
9:30 – 9:45	Ludovic JASON (CEA)	Welcome Address
9:45 – 10:00	Isabelle CHATAIGNER, (French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Space)	Opening Remarks: European Innovation Perspective
10:00 – 10:40	Nadja ADAMOVIĆ (TU Wien) Iacob CRUCIANU, Otilia BULARCA (SIMAVI) Jesper FRIIS (SINTEF) Geoffrey DANIEL (CEA) Patrice TOCHON (GENVIA) Giuseppe MINAFRA (RINA)	MatCHMaker Results & Industrial Exploitation Pathways <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Interoperable semantic frameworks and ontologies• Open Repository & AI-enabled solutions• Industrial integration and sustainability models
10:40 – 11:00	Iacob CRUCIANU (SIMAVI)	Live Demonstration <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Open Repository functionality• Tool interoperability in practice
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee & Networking Break	
11:30 - 12:15	Moderator: Alexandre OUZIA (Heidelberg Materials) Panellists: Julian DE MARCHI (Netherlands Aerospace Centre), Marzuk KAMAL (AeonX AI), Jean-Yves DELANNOY (Arkema), Pierre KIENER (Michelin)	Panel I: From Project Results to Industrial Adoption <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integration into R&D workflows• Adoption barriers & scalability strategies• Bridging research outcomes & industrial implementation

12:15 – 13:30	Lunch & Networking Break	
13:30 – 14:15	Alexandre OUZIA (Heidelberg Materials)	<p>White Paper on Data Lifecycles & Non-Technical Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic recommendations Alignment across European initiatives • Overcoming non-technical adoption barriers
14:15 -14:45	Simon STIER (Fraunhofer ISC)	<p>Materials Commons as a Strategic Exploitation Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable digital infrastructure • Federated integration of EU project results • Cross-project & cross-border collaboration pathways
14:45 – 15:15	Coffee & Networking Break	
15:15 – 16:00	<p>Moderator: Gerhard GOLDBECK (EMMC)</p> <p>Panellists: Simon STIER (Fraunhofer ISC), Ennio CAPRIA (ESRF), Marek CEBECAUER (Czech Academy of Sciences)</p>	<p>Panel II: Open Data, Standards, Policy & Strategic Outlook</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability & metadata standards • Governance & long-term infrastructure sustainability • Strategic priorities for Europe's digital materials ecosystem
16:00 onwards	Discussion & Networking	<p>Targeted Business & Collaboration Exchange</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry-research matchmaking • Horizon Europe synergies • Future collaboration opportunities